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PERCEPTIONS OF ALLIED MEDICAL STUDENTS TOWARD ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID 19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The global outbreak of COVID-19 has resulted in the most significant disruption to education systems in history, impacting educators and students across a range of educational institutions from primary to tertiary level (United Nations, 2020). The lockdown has resulted in a significant shift in learning methods from in-person instruction to online learning, with some institutions even closing as a result of the suspension of classes. The research intended to determine the perceptions of allied medical course students towards online learning, to find their reaction to the transition from face-to-face to online implementation of classes, perceived advantages and disadvantages, and their overall preference based on their experience during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study used a descriptive qualitative research design and is deemed appropriate since the study

aimed to find out the perceptions of the Bachelor of Medical Laboratory Science students about online learning during the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. The study has unraveled the initial reaction of the BMLS Students to Online Classes such that (1) Students were excited and; (2) worried; (3) Some students remained neutral. On the other hand, Students' Perceptions about Online Learning can be Advantageous and have unearthed the following themes: (1) it is more flexible (2) it is convenient (3) it allows students to study at their own pace (4) it gives them the comfort of studying at home ; (5) it reduces risk of COVID-19 transmission as well as Disadvantageous where the students perceived online learning as disadvantageous as (1) it highly requires a stable internet connection (2) it is uncomfortable to communicate online (3) it negatively affects the study habits or lifestyle of students (4) it encourages students to be unproductive due to its flexibility (5) it deprives students from determining areas for self-improvement since there is lack of guidance and feedback from teachers and instructors; (6) it does not facilitate practical application of theoretical knowledge; (7) it does not motivate the students to actively participate since there the teachers or instructors cannot monitor the students from their end. However, the students' Preference is Face-to-Face Classes as classes provide a more dynamic way of learning and it offers a lot more in terms of different learning methods to be utilized individually or as a whole class. The conduct of face-to-face classes requires medical students to be actively involved in the learning process.

Keywords: *Perceptions, Medical Students, Online Learning, Pandemic*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused the largest disruption of education systems in history, affecting learners and teachers in various institutions around the world from primary to higher education (United Nations, 2020). The lockdown has led to the suspension of classes and even the closure of several institutions, creating a drastic change in learning methods from face-to-face classes to online learning. This shift in instructional delivery has become a great challenge to schools that offer technical, practical, and clinical training courses that require hands-on experience in learning such as in technical and vocational education and training institutions and some other universities, especially medical schools.

To minimize the impact of this education disruption, medical schools had to find another approach and that is through the use of electronic learning (e-learning), online learning or web-based learning as the core method of teaching medical students.

Mahajan, M. V., & Kalpana, R. (2020) defined electronic learning (e-learning) as a means of education that incorporates electronic equipment and tools, and the interactivity that occurs between these and the people involved in the educational process such as the instructors and learners.

E-learning can deliver “new” information not contained in traditional sources, effectively reinforcing other course information through offering examples, explanations, assessments, and exercises. In this way, online instruction can potentially enhance learning compared to what can be accomplished using a classroom-only approach (McEwen, 1997). In addition to that, e-learning offers flexibility and convenience in a way

that the students can access and learn the materials given to them anywhere and anytime they desire.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research intended to determine the perceptions of allied medical course students towards online learning, to find their reaction to the transition from face-to-face to online implementation of classes, perceived advantages and disadvantages, and their overall preference based on their experience during the COVID-19 pandemic.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive qualitative research design. This design is deemed appropriate since the study aimed to find out the perceptions of the students about online learning during the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic which also includes the initial reaction of the BMLS Students about online classes, positive and negative impacts of online learning to the BMLS students during the pandemic, and students' preference between online learning over traditional learning.

Research Participants

The respondents of this study were 10 students who came from BMLS levels III and IV enrolled at Doña Remedios Trinidad Romualdez Educational Foundation, Tacloban City. They were the students who experienced the transition from traditional face-to-face learning to online learning and were selected by using the Simple Random Sampling (SRS) method via the Fishbowl technique of their sections in the SY 2021-2022.

Data Analysis

After the interview was done, the researchers transcribed and translated the recording into English. When the final transcription of the interview was done, the researchers coded the data to identify recurrent themes in the following specific problem areas: (a) the initial reaction of BMLS students about online classes; (b) students' perceptions about online learning; and (c) preference for face-to-face classes. The identified themes served as the basis in the discussion of results and formulation of conclusions and recommendation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Initial Reaction of the BMLS Students about Online Classes

From the participants' answers to the interview questions, the themes that emerged relative to the initial reaction of the BMLS students about online classes are: (1) Students were excited and; (2) worried; (3) Some students remained neutral.

Students were excited. Students find it exciting at first, as they are curious of what to expect and experience during the online learning setup.

I was excited because uhm most of our lessons were conducted face to face and online classes would be like a change from the usual educational setup (Transcript 3, Line 2, Page 3). My initial reaction was....it was exciting at first but then, when we... got to uhh... experience online class for a long time na uhm, it was boring and not conducive ...for me as a learner (Transcript 9, Line , Page 9).

As cited from the research of Agung (2020), students perceived online meetings as fun but the downside was that the students could not stand with the marathon assignments in the long run. From the similar study mentioned, it revealed that most students were actively involved in online learning but only 33.3% were enthusiastic. In relation to the study conducted, it could be deduced that after the excitement and hopeful perspectives, over time the students lose excitement and perceived its exhausting side, losing enthusiasm or excitement.

Students were worried. The sudden transition from traditional learning to online learning setup made the students feel worried because they are accustomed to face-to-face classes.

Eh.. The online classes were abrupt - it has always been a habit of mine to take classes face to face (from pre-school up until now). And so, it made me worried whether I'll be able to properly digest the lessons from this type of learning. It took some time for me to adjust to the current situation (Transcript 4, Line 10, Page 4).

My initial reaction was I was surprised. I eventually thought if it is only going to be temporary or it will be continuous (Transcript 7, Line , Page 7).

First and foremost, it is of course hard to process or think about the sudden change of learning method because, throughout the years of studying, I get used to the normal way of learning... (Transcript 8, Line 2, Page 8).

uhm...what do you call this? Personally uhm like I honestly disagree. Like reacted right away about why, is it okay for me to talk in waray-waray or tagalog? (Transcript 10, Line 2, Page 10)

The study of Agung et al., (2020), revealed that most students were actively involved in online learning, however, it did not mean that they were enthusiastic. Most of the, 66.7% of students were not enthusiastic. This is in line with the findings of the present study as the respondents were worried about the conduct of online learning.

Some students remained neutral. Students foresee and weigh the positive and negative outcomes of the new learning setup considering that there is a health threat which is the COVID-19 pandemic, thus remaining neutral.

Like... Partly, 50/50 because, it was like, there was a part that.... the outcome was positive in my perspective towards online learning. But, there are also negative outcomes for me (Transcript 1, Line 2, Page 1).

At first, it was new to me and I had mixed emotions, mixed reaction. Good that it is online considering that Covid (transmission) could be lessened and it is good that you just stay at home because many resources are available...what makes it hard is if your internet connection is not strong but on my part it is just fine (Transcript 2, Line 2, Page 2).

My initial reaction to the changes... I didn't really care whether uhmm online or uhh face-to-face. I assumed that the same quality of teaching would be carried over to online classes. So initially, I really did not mind (Transcript 5, Line 2, Page 5).

It shows that students liked online learning because of the easy access to lecture notes anywhere, anytime without being present in classes and students can receive better explanations of the course content compared with traditional learning

Students' Perceptions of Online Learning

Advantageous. From the interview conducted with the participants, the students perceived online learning as advantageous since (1) it is more flexible (2) it is convenient (3) it allows students to study at their own pace (4) it gives them the comfort of studying at home ; (5) it reduces the risk of COVID-19 transmission.

...you have a lot more time in your hands compared to when it was face-to- face classes. Transcript 1, Line 4,Page 1

Good that it is online considering that COVID-19 (transmission) could be lessened and it is good that you just stay at home because many resources are available... Transcript 2, Line 2, Page 2

For me, in general, it is better considering that it allows you to record and allows them to give you files of recorded lectures. You can replay. So, for that part in general, my online class is okay. Transcript 2, Line 8, Page 2

Uhm, positive experience, maybe online classes for me it is more flexible compared to the face to face for me that's the positive aspect. Transcript 3, Line 6, Page 3

This learning method is convenient to both students and teachers. For one, instructors can conveniently upload their activities and lectures at, at, at, at the safety of their homes (without necessarily going to school). Students can also easily access any lessons provided that the instructors already publish their lessons) anytime and anywhere if there is intern-internet connection. Also, this type of learning as I've said, it greatly reduces the transmission of covid-19. Transcript 4, Line 16, Page 4

At least, now I can do things besides working at home and get back to my studies after. Transcript 6, Line 2, Page 6

Because I was in the comfort of my home while studying. Transcript 6, Line 4, Page 6

On the positive side, since it's recorded you can go back to the topics that you've missed or you didn't understand. Transcript 7, Line 10, Page 6

As a slow-paced learner, it was kind of advantageous, because you, like what I said in the previous question you can go back to the topics that you've missed and you didn't understand and they give time to conduct quizzes and exams so yeah it was a bit advantageous. Transcript 7, Line 12, Page 7

I can clearly manage my schedule for the whole month or for the whole academic year. And it becomes a way of learning to look for ah- more references of a certain topic especially if I cannot understand those files given by our CI as well as, ah- it helps me to think critically and accurately everytime I study because of course, it's like in the online learning, most of the time you are the one who teaches yourself. Transcript 8, Line 4, Page 8

Advantageous for some uhh...for those who prefer to study alone. Transcript 9, Line 6, Page 9

It's in my own pace and what do you call this? I'm not pressured to study right away, so I can rest anytime I want. Transcript 10, Line 8, Page 9

Previous studies revealed the same results as the findings of Chandrasiri & Weerakoon (2022) stated that the majority of their student respondents perceived that online learning is flexible, convenient, allows students to learn at their own pace, could save time than traditional learning, and an effective way to control the spread of COVID-19.

Disadvantageous. Based on the interview conducted, the students perceived online learning as disadvantageous as (1) it highly requires a stable internet connection (2) it is uncomfortable to communicate online (3) it negatively affects the study habits or lifestyle of students (4) it encourages students to be unproductive due to its flexibility (5) it deprives students of determining areas for self-improvement since there is lack of guidance and feedback from teachers and instructors; (6) it does not facilitate practical application of theoretical knowledge; (7) it does not motivate the students to actively participate since there the teachers or instructors cannot monitor the students from their end.

...but the downside is that it heavily requires a stable internet connection and access to gadgets. Transcript 1, Line 4, Page 1

Mostly, the experience was disadvantageous especially that our course specializes in the medical field which is mostly skill-based but then, our laboratories were only done online. We were only doing lectures and watching videos of lab procedures that we should be doing. There was no practical application of these procedures as if

we were just imagining it. Although, the theoreticals were important, it is also important for us to be able to perform such procedures. Transcript 1, Line 10, Page 1

...what makes it hard is if your internet connection is not strong but on my part it is just fine. Transcript 2, Line 2, Page 2

During online class, I get nervous in online reporting, during recitation I like I don't know there are lots of uhmm watching and listening and your environment [laughs] for me recitation is better, quizzes are better if face- to-face because if it is held online it's like you become lazy and there are lots of factors that can affect you and lots of distractions, so what I feel about the conduct of online class is that it is disadvantageous because I prefer face-to-face. Transcript 2, Line 4, Page 2

But the negative aspect is that for me, since it was almost I mean everything was online it was a change of my routine which for me made me lazy, unproductive and also change in lifestyle because I wasn't it wasn't a dynamic way of learning so for me it wasn't it isn't for me, so. Transcript 3, Line 6, Page 3

Uhh for me in general it's a disadvantage for me because uhh aside from learning here in the college I also tried online classes from other schools it was fine but in the general setting and especially for third year wherein we have the major subjects its disadvantageous because of its setup and I think it's like learning face-to-face and at school interacting with the teacher and the classmates is more helpful in learning compared to the online platform. Transcript 3, Line 8, Page 3

It felt like I was just watching some online lectures from YouTube (except that the online classes are more formal and accre- accredited). And unlike face-to-face sessions, online classes are a lot more laid back. I mean, I could just sleep, play video games, or eat during lectures without the instructor, instructor knowing – and this made not take the online classes seriously. And of course, internet, internet signal fluctuation is also a problem – a single drop of signal is enough to disrupt the whole class session. These are just few of the downsides of online learning. Transcript 4, Line 14, Page 4

Uhm, Consequently, if students don't have internet access – or, at least, they don't have proper internet connection – they won't be able to access the lectures and activities of the teacher. And quizzes and exams online, in this learning method can be easily cheated on. Transcript 4, Line 16, Page 4

One of the disadvantages of online learning here in RTRMF is on the lack of guidance and feedback and in ensuring that what we are learning is right or something like that. It's like they only depend on books or on the self-learning that they leave behind their duties. Transcript 5, Line 7, Page 5

Overall, I think like it is disadvantageous for me, disadvantageous but benefit of the doubt for RTRMF I just feel like they just did not adjust properly. But if we are talking about online classes as a whole let's say if there was proper guidance and it was implemented properly... I think it could be a force for good. But as of now, what has happened to RTR and our third year level and from senior level also it was not advantageous. Face-to-face is better. Transcript 5, Line 9, Page 5

The downside is that, you can't focus because of the home environment. Our minds are not conditioned when we are not in an academic environment. The lack of pressure from school and interaction from your peers, teachers made the learning process from school more different. Transcript 6, Line 4, Page 6

Oh, it was very... difficult to adjust because...what do you call it. You think like you are just in your room and you feel lazy. You don't have like, you don't have a separation between school life and your private personal life so yes, it was like hard to adjust because you are just online, camera is off, microphone is off so how will your professor know that you are participating or not. Transcript 7, Line 8, Page 7

About the negative, you're lazy to do work, you're lazy to listen and your attention span is not that long. Transcript 7, Line 10, Page 7

And so, for the negative impact, due to a big adjustment my study habit was no longer the same just like before. Online learning mostly is un- motivational from the fact that you are not sure all the time to what you are teaching to yourself eh ah...- it is it true or your understanding from the topic if it is enough already. Transcript 8, Line 4, Page 8

the teacher cannot thoroughly asses what do you call this? If the participant or students are truly listening and they are not obliged to listen because uhm...we are not being observed and then if the discussion is too long, it's not that engaging because there is no uhm no interaction. (Transcript 10, Line 6, Page 10)

...it's because since it's in my own pace, there are times that I don't study much and there are also times that I study too much that I experience burnout and the I tend to overthink because I don't know how much my other peers have studied and where in the lessons they are already at and...uhm...what do you call this? I'm not motivated from this kind of learning platform. It's like...sometimes I can't attend lectures because the signal is not great usually and it's like, sometimes the teacher's way of discussing you can't really ask questions or you get too shy to ask. (Transcript 10, Line 8, Page 10)

The findings of the study support that of Chandrasiri & Weerakoon (2022) as their students perceived online learning as challenging since it is hard to establish a good

internet connection, it is less motivating as there is less interaction with lecturers, and it is difficult to learn clinically based subjects. Also, it agrees with Agung et al. (2020) that the availability of the Internet is their weakness.

Preferences for Face-to-Face Classes

According to the interviews conducted, students prefer face-to-face classes over online classes.

Face-to-face classes provide a more dynamic way of learning as it offers a lot more in terms of different learning methods to be utilized individually or as a whole class. The conduct of face-to-face classes requires medical students to be actively involved in the learning process.

Uhh face-to-face. Since we, medical technologists are more in the laboratory, so by that we practice the handling of laboratory equipment. Face-to-face is better because you get to ask in real-time to our teachers. And then hmmm that is all considering that we are medical technologists so (we focus on) laboratories so that is why we really need the face-to-face setup. Do you still have additional... Maybe I was not able to... (Transcript 2, Line 10, Page 2)

Uhm definitely face to face because uhm our course, our subject, it is uh very important in the medical field so when we learn things, I think it's better that we learn it with the professional, with the instructors and also with our classmates because very redundant, but dynamic way of learning is more effective for uhm learning and then understanding the concepts because the concepts are not easy to learn and learning them from home is not the best environment to study. (Transcript 3, Line 10, Page 3)

According to the feedback given by the respondents, they prefer face-to-face classes with the common reason being that the field of study requires practical skill application partnered with theoretical knowledge, which, the online method of learning fails to offer.

Face-to-face classes allow practical application of theories and concepts which is the biggest flaw of online learning methods. Conducting on-site skill development through practical performances and demonstrations is essential in molding competent allied medical professionals.

I'd prefer face-to-face. because the procedures that were being taught during lectures are being performed by us rather than just observing how our lecturers perform these tests. In other words. on-hand procedures. Like, you learn how to perform the procedure by practicing during laboratory experimentations because this is vital as we enter our internship and even as far as when we finally work in a laboratory. (Transcript 1, Line 14, Page 1)

Uhm, while online learning is advantageous in some aspects, face-to-face learning is still the best learning method. Face-to-face classes are more hands-on compared to online classes. As health

practitioners, it should be always noted that practical skills are as – if not, more – essential as the knowledge we get from books. It would be of no use if we don't know how to apply the principles of our learnings in our practice. (Transcript 4, Line 18, Page 4)

A study done by AlQhtani, A., AlSwedan, N., Almulhim, A. *et al.* (2021) results agree with the aforementioned statement. 358 medical students who come from different universities in Saudi Arabia were involved in the study. It is important to note that 282 or nearly 75% of the respondents have no first-hand experience in attending medical classes online before the pandemic. Although results showed that online learning was found to be convenient and effective for learning by the respondents, the majority of them found it difficult to balance practical application and theoretical knowledge compared to the traditional classroom teaching. In other words, a field of studies that requires skill expression aside from theoretical mastery would result in less effective mastery in the practical application of procedures.

A study done by Kuriakose, A. *et al* (2021) supports this claim. 801 medical students coming from various institutions were part of the study. Results of the study showed that 74% of the respondents have a negative perception towards online learning. 64% of the respondents found that hands-on learning (practical application) was technically lacking and uncondusive and also, 70% responded lack of clinical learning which not only mean that practical skill expression was not being practiced enough but also, the foundation for theoretical knowledge of clinical studies is also inadequate for optimal results in assessments.

Face-to-face classes are more motivating and engaging which stimulates the students' curiosity to learn. Students would strike to balance school, personal growth and development in face-to-face classes.

Prefer the most... I would say, I enjoy face-to-face classes because it gives you a routine to follow. One of the difficult things about online classes...it's like nothing pushes you to wake up early in the morning because submission in online class is up until twelve midnight and so. You can still procrastinate whereas in face-to-face class you are pushed to really know how to answer the quiz because there is a set time limit for answering. You can't do it throughout the day. And then it forces you to go to school. I guess what is good also is for the regularity for your life so that you have a routine or something like that but when it comes to...I prefer the face-to-face overall. (Transcript 5, Line 15, Page 5)

Face-to-face, that was also the reason you get to interact and get to focus because that is the environment you were acuminated to study. And also, you get to be good influenced because everyone around you is focused and centered. Also, you get to share your knowledge with your peers and also confer with your professors. (Transcript 6, Line 12, Page 1)

For me, face-to-face because you get to interact with your classmates and also with your professor. You get to interact also in online class but it's different because you get shy, you get anxiety, you get embarrassed like if you have asked the wrong question. So of course, in face-to-face, after class you can ask. If you don't understand you ask your classmates. And it's almost like, you enjoy face-to-face because you do have a school life. There is a boundary between your school life and your personal life. So, yes, I do prefer face-to-face. Transcript 7, Line 14, Page 7)

I cannot say I prefer online learning over that the traditional learning. Because it really hits different if we are physically in the school and listening to our professors based on their teaching and there's a high tendency that you can understand well the topics accordingly. So, I'm, I'm in the side of the face-to-face classes. -that's it. (Transcript 8, Line 8, Page)

I prefer face-to-face classes because what do you call this? It has, the interaction is very engaging, so if your seat is in the front row, you can listen well and the discussion will remain in your head and also you are encouraging to read or you are motivated to learn because of your environment like for example.... your friends and what do you call this? Classmates. You can see them that they are willing to learn or study...and also...where are we now? Uhm that's all...I really like face-to-face because what do you call this? Even if I had to commute, even if I get tired, it's still fine with me because of the interaction with other people you can ask questions, they can help you, there are a lot of stories to tell, that's why. And usually in online there is a lot of chismis and can cause a lot of distractions. There are a lot of social media so it's not that good. That's all. (Transcript 10, Line 4, Page)

The result of the interpretation of the themes showed that the respondents' perception towards online education tends to be mostly negative the common issue being the lack of interaction of students with their teachers and peers and also, insufficient feedback from teachers. Additionally, the course content, learning materials, and progress tracking of students also had a major impact on the participants' motivational levels. Looking back to the aforementioned negative issues, the students' motivation is quite negatively impacted which would result in poor performance in activities in online activities and sessions. Lastly, participants had difficulty managing their self-discipline to follow the courses' schedules set by the faculty despite a decent degree of satisfaction with the course content. Also, it was noted they had difficulty maintaining their attention span during synchronous lessons even for a short period.

In a nutshell, the respondents stated their various perceptions towards online education which mostly comes off negatively. The various reasons as to why their motivation to learn is significantly hindered is due to dissatisfaction with the course content and materials, lack of self-discipline to follow the course by the set schedules,

lack of communication towards peers, and insufficient feedback from the teachers in regards to their progress.

Conclusions

In light of the findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Based on the findings, students were anxious for several reasons yet remained positive about the transition of learning setup from the traditional to online as they were also curious about what to experience during its implementation.

Online learning was found to be more disadvantageous rather than advantageous based on the responses of the students to the interview.

The results of the interview reflected that most respondents prefer face-to-face classes rather than online learning due to disadvantages perceived by the students of the latter.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions derived, recommendations to improve online learning setup are suggested.

Schedules, requirements, and activities presented and discussed during orientation must be strictly followed so that the students and teachers could have ample time to make preparations and adjustments beforehand.

It would be highly recommended that teachers should explore more and learn to maximize the use of the online learning platform provided by the educational institution which is Canvas. The use of discussion or forum and collaboration in Canvas in which both students and teachers could ask and share knowledge about a certain topic or for feedback could increase engagement from students. Evaluation of grades section on the said online platform should be checked and updated regularly by the teachers and instructors so the students can keep track of their academic status or standing and be able to improve their study habits when needed.

The school should organize seminars and symposiums to help students gain clarity, knowledge, and a positive attitude toward online learning.

Researchers should include students from other college departments for a wider scope of respondents and to improve the reliability of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethics is an integral part of conducting research, especially when the proponents are dealing with the people, the community, pertinent documents, animals, and the like. An absolute observance was done and followed by the ethical consideration in conducting this study to avoid fallacy or misconceptions of the participant's views about the phenomenon under study, its integrity, and most especially to protect them from any harm by hiding their personal information using John Doe names. Lastly, the proponent asked the approval of the consent form from the participants, stating their rights and privileges including their role in the research.

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To God be the glory.

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